

Bias in Numbers Part 3: Paradoxes of Infinity, 0 as Infinitesimal and the Logic of Superposition

By Allan Porter

“One who spends his entire life counting to infinity will die no closer to infinity than he started”

Defining Infinity

The concept of infinity is one of the most ambiguous semantic concoctions. From “that which has no limits” to the “highest possible number”, it can be said that infinity has as many definitions as it does digits. There are similarly an “infinite” amount of “amalgamations” of infinity. From the cardinality of all rational numbers to the set of numbers between 1 and 2 to those between 1 and 3, one need not look far to find infinity rearing its cagey head in mathematics.

Finding an Arithmetic Home For Infinity

However, despite its elusive nature, can there be a means of mathematically representing infinity in relation to finite numbers? For example, just as a half of something could be arithmetically conceived as “something”/2 can infinity possess a similar relation to an “arithmetic” something?

Well if infinity is defined mathematically as “the highest possible number” then it can be “arithmetically conceived” in its relation to 0 which is the “lowest possible number” (*Number here in its absolute sense*). For if 0 is defined as the absolute floor of all numbers, then infinity would need to be defined as the absolute ceiling of all numbers.

Is Infinity The Inverse of 0?

One issue here is that many contemporary mathematicians don’t consider infinity as the “inverse” of 0, but rather as the inverse of a number that is “infinitesimal” or just above 0. The reason for this is because it’s an intuitive leap to think that any amount of 0’s can actually add up to equal anything but 0. The philosophical question that therefore arises here is the following: is the opposite of everything (infinity), nothing (0) or rather the smallest possible tangible thing (infinitesimal)? I would argue that the latter (an infinitesimal number) cannot possibly exist since if it was a nonzero size it could always be divided further and further and never actually be infinitesimal. In fact the only indivisible number that actually exists is 0 since once 0 is reached any division within it would still result in only 0. Therefore even though it is difficult to understand how any amount of “zeros” could add up to something tangible, I believe that if such a “infinitesimal” number exists it would need to be zero since if it wasn’t it can’t be infinitesimal since it wouldn’t actually be indivisible. Again, this is because any conceivable number no matter how small could still be divided by 10 (or any finite integer) and yield a number smaller than itself. Only 0 however could be divided by 10 and still be 0. This is because 0 is the only actual indivisible number.

Note that such a 0 would not simply indicate “nothing” but rather act as a physical zero such as a zero dimensional coordinate point a la Massimo Melli’s logon. Such a physical zero is not merely the ‘absence of quantity’ but itself a zero dimensional size-less point that’s only feature is that of position and being “here” rather than “there”.

Can 0 be Infinitesimal?

Since every quantity that is divisible needs to at its core be composed of “indivisible components” I would argue that such “indivisible” components could be called “0” even if they are actually “something” since 0 is defined as much by its “indivisibility” as its lack of quantity. However the question then is: if “0” exists as an indivisible “root of all numbers”, then wouldn’t multiple 0’s multiplied together need to equal to a real number? Why would multiple 0’s put together still be indivisible if every 0 actually consists of “something”? Surely two zeroes together could be divided into just one of those zeros! The answer to this is that since 0 is “size-less” any finite number of 0’s multiplied together would still tend to be size-less just as how any divisions within infinity would still need to be “infinite”.

To demonstrate this, imagine a one dimensional line with a length of 10. Essentially such a line contains an infinite amount of infinitesimal coordinates as any number within it between 0 and 10 could always be divided further and further until every individual number within the line is indivisible. Obviously, this means that there would be an infinite amount of such points in the line. Now what would happen if 1 coordinate was removed from this line? Well there would still be an infinite amount of points within the line itself since the line would still need to be divided into indivisible components of which there will be an infinite number. Now what would happen if the line was cut in half? Well still there would need to be an infinite amount of points in the resulting lines. In fact, no matter how many finite divisions are made in this line, it wouldn’t matter - the resulting line would still contain an infinite amount of infinitesimal “points” or coordinates.

This shows that anytime an infinite value is divided into a finite number of divisions, the resulting number of components in each division will still be infinity. So too, the same logic can be used for 0. If there are 2 zero dimensional coordinates drawn on an axis then still no line of any finite size would result. For since these two coordinates are just zero dimensional “points” together they can never make up anything with a “real size” in one dimension. In fact it will take an infinite amount of such coordinates to actually ever add up to a “real line” of finite size. This is simply because - it is known that any finite number of zero dimensional points put together is still of size 0. However it is also known that any finite sized line is made of zero dimensional points. Therefore the only conclusion would be that a finite sized line must be composed of an infinite amount of zero dimensional points (or physical 0’s). Furthermore, this compares to infinity since no matter how many times infinity is divided, each division within it would still be “infinitely sized”. However, since “anything” that exists is essentially a division of infinity, then surely infinity CAN be divided. However, since any finite number multiple by anything finite will always not be infinity (since such a number can always be multiplied further), then it can be reasoned that only when multiplied by infinity can any finite number become infinity which implies that only when infinity is divided by infinity can the resulting divisions each be finite. This shows the relationship between 0 and infinity - just as there is an “infinite threshold” when

multiplying 0 by anything in order to get something finite, there is an “infinite threshold” when dividing infinity by anything in order to get something finite.

In this way (where X is any finite number):

$$\infty / X = \infty$$

$$0 * X = 0$$

$$0 * \infty = X$$

$$\infty / \infty = X$$

Now that it has been shown how 0 is in fact a “size-less” entity that still at the same time makes up every finite number, 0’s status as not only 0 but also as the true “infinitesimal” number could be established. In this way 0 can be referred to as the true “absolute floor of all numbers”. Similarly, there can be no number larger than infinity since infinity cannot be multiplied (because it already includes all other numbers). Therefore, infinity must be “the absolute ceiling of all numbers”.

In order to understand the implications of this distinction, think of the corollary $y = 0/x$ where y is always equal to 0 no matter the non-zero value of x. The reasoning for this of course is since 0 is infinitely small, it is indivisible and can therefore never be broken down into any parts smaller than itself (0). Therefore, no matter the amount of “divisions” there would be to divide 0 into, it is already indivisible since it is at the lowest possible value. This is why 0 is always 0 no matter the nonzero denominator; since it is impossible to divide 0 (because it is already indivisible), what it is being divided into does not matter or affect its value (since it is already an indivisible 0).

Now using this logic of 0 as the “floor” of all numbers, then perhaps opposing properties could be assigned to infinity which is the “ceiling of all numbers”. Furthermore, since infinity is the inverse of 0 and division is the inverse of multiplication, then just as 0 is “indivisible” infinity would need to be “un-multipliable”. This idea of infinity not being “multipliable” is also intuitive since infinity is already the ceiling of all numbers and would therefore be unable to be multiplied. Now if 0 as the floor of all numbers could be described by $0/x$ (since 0 is already indivisible, the x here wouldn’t matter), then its inverse (the ceiling of all numbers - infinity) should intuitively be described by $x/0$.

Now the actual logic for $X/0$ representing infinity is as follows: Since 0 is indivisible and cannot be grouped into anything (since it’s already the smallest possible quantity), so too infinity could be described by its absence of groups since there are no “bounds” or limits on its quantity. Therefore, since there are no limits to infinity’s quantity, its denominator should always be 0 (thus the $x/0$). The reason for this is just as how 0’s denominator did not matter since its numerator (0) is always indivisible, so too infinity would need to be a number that is always divided into 0 groups (since if it was something that was divided into any number of groups that wasn’t zero such a number would not be infinite).

Using this logic, if $0/x$ can be used to describe 0, then 0’s inverse - infinity should be able to be represented by $x/0$. Furthermore, just as how in $0/x$, the nonzero value of x doesn’t matter

(since $0/x$ is still 0), so too the nonzero x in $x/0$ shouldn't matter either (since $x/0$ is still infinity since if any number was split into a finite amount of groups such a number could not be infinity).

Testing $X/0$ as Infinity

In order to test this intuition of $X/0$ as ∞ (where X is any positive non-zero number), take the statement $1/n$ and substitute in smaller and smaller numbers for n .

For example:

$$1/2 = .5$$

$$1/1 = 1$$

$$1/.5 = 2$$

$$1/.25 = 4$$

$$1/.1 = 10$$

$$1/.01 = 100$$

$$1/.001 = 1000$$

It can be seen from here that as n tends closer and closer to 0, $1/n$ can be evaluated as 'tending closer and closer to infinity'. The 'tending to 0' n here is therefore perfectly inversely proportional to the increasing solution which tends to infinity. However, is "tending towards infinity" the same as "infinity"? After all perhaps since 0 can never be definitively reached in the denominator of $1/n$ as n decreases (since the number of significant 0's in the denominator of $1/n$ can be expanded limitlessly), then perhaps there is also no proof that infinity can ever be reached in the solution either?

Well since we have proven that infinitely smaller numbers are inversely proportional to infinitely larger numbers, I would argue that we have already proved that $X/0 = \infty$. This is because all 0 really is is an "infinitely small number" while all ∞ is is an "infinitely large number". Therefore stating that "infinitely smaller numbers" are inversely proportional to "infinitely large numbers" as is done in $\lim (n \rightarrow 0): 1/n$ is the same as stating that their extremes are proportional (or that 0 is inversely proportional to ∞). For since $X/0$ is the inverse of $0/X$ and since the $0/x$ can be called 0, it should be concluded that the $X/0$ can similarly be called "infinity". (This again is because infinity is only defined as something inversely proportional to 0 so of course should be able to be defined by 0's arithmetic inverse in terms of its representation).

Therefore, both 0 and $x/0$ can be considered inversely proportional since they are perfectly unreachable in opposite directions. Moreover, perhaps no proof should have been needed as this should have been obvious based off their definitions alone. After all, if 0 is an absence of quantity and ∞ is a totality of quantity then it should be implied that the two are opposites and therefore inversely proportional. For this reason, there should be no counter-intuitiveness at all in describing ∞ as $x/0$ since 0 can of course be described by $0/x$ and the two are inversely proportional.

Does $\infty = \infty$?

One issue that always surfaces when comparing infinity to 0 is its inherent inequality. For there is an argument that since there is only one mathematical instantiation of 0 and multiple instantiations of ∞ , the two can never coexist in an equation like $1/0 = \infty$. This can be seen by comparing $1/0$ and $2/0$. Surely, both $1/0$ and $2/0$ could not be equal to another as that would imply that 1 is equal to 2! Therefore, there is a belief that there are “different sized” infinities even though infinity at the same time is meant to indicate the largest possible size in existence!

Solving This Paradox

How many numbers are there between 0 and 1?

This paradox of “unequal infinities” can be solved in this way: Take the example of trying to determine how many possible numbers there are in between 0 and 1. In order to do this, significant zeros must be continuously added behind each decimal (ie .01 to .001, .02 to .002, .03 to .003) of every possible number between 0 and 1 until each number is infinitely small. Therefore it can be said that until every single possible number between 0 and 1 can no longer be subdivided, there would be more possible numbers in the set of numbers between 0 and 1. This is of course because even a number like 10^{-20} can be subdivided smaller into 10^{-21} simply by dividing it by 10.

Since 0 is obviously the only number that is indivisible, until each number between 0 and 1 is individually equal to “0” there would still be more numbers unaccounted for between 0 and 1. Therefore, the amount of numbers between 0 and 1, can be defined by the equation $1/0 = X$. This is because what “the amount of numbers between 0 and 1” is actually asking is “how many indivisible numbers are there between 0 and 1”. Since 0 is the only indivisible number, then “the amount of indivisible numbers between 0 and 1” would of course need to be: the distance between 0 and 1 (which of course is 1) / the value of each indivisible number in between (which of course is 0 since 0 is the only number that's indivisible).

Therefore, asking for the amount of numbers between “0 and 1” is the same as asking “ $1/0$ ”. Now of course since there are an infinite amount of numbers between 0 and 1 (since another number between 0 and 1 could always be added by dividing an existing number between 0 and 1 by 10), then there are essentially an “infinite” amount of numbers between 0 and 1, since the value in question “goes on forever”. Similarly, it can be seen that $1/0$ is also infinity since it “goes on forever”.

How many numbers are there between 0 and 2?

Now when attempting to find the amount of numbers between 0 and 2, the same logic could be applied. There would need to be an infinite amount of numbers between 0 and 2 since an existing number between 0 and 2 could always be divided further by 10 thus adding in another number to the set. Again this would need to be done until each number is indivisible and equal to 0 thus equating the amount of numbers between 0 and 2 to “the difference between 0 and 2” (2) / the value of each indivisible number between 0 and 2 (0). Therefore it can be seen that the number of possible numbers between 0 and 2 is $2/0$.

However, commonly it is thought that since the set of numbers between 0 and 2 would need to include the set of numbers between 0 and 1 that the set of numbers between 0 and 2 is larger. For after all, the possible numbers between 0 and 2 would need to be equal to all the possible numbers between 0 and 1 + all of the numbers between 1 and 2. Therefore, how can there be the same amount of quantity between 0 and 2 as there is between 0 and 1 if the amount of numbers between 0 and 2 must by definition be 2 times the amount of numbers in 0 to 1!?

Well since every number between 0 and 1 can forever be subdivided (until 0 is reached, which it never will be), and the same can be said of the numbers between 0 and 2, then the number of numbers between 0 and 1 can be said to be described in the same way as the number of numbers between 0 and 2 in that they both continue endlessly or are “limitless”. This would mean they both contain an “infinite” number of 0 sized components and that they are both limitless in their expansions. When the set of one expands, the set of the other expands and since they both expand infinitely and never “stop” expanding, it can’t be said that one set has more numbers than the other.

This essentially is because the words “more” and “less” are relative words used to describe a difference in finiteness. However, in order for a set of numbers to be “finite”, the set of numbers must “stop expanding” and be “confined” to only a specific cardinality. If the cardinality of a set however never ceases and is limitless in its expansion, then it would never reach such a stop (since it is infinite). For there would always be more divisions of the numbers in the set possible to “count” and therefore such a set would never be sufficiently “confined” and finite in order for measurement to take place.

Infinity Cannot Be Measured

Therefore, the words “more” and “less” do not apply to infinite sets since they presuppose finiteness. This is because comparing one “set of numbers” relative to another in terms of their size requires “measurement” on the part of the observer. Measurement itself requires confinement of the values of the sets so the measurer can essentially take a “snapshot” of one set and compare it to the other set. However, if the sets are infinitely expanding such a “snapshot” never takes place. In this way anything infinite (such as an infinite set of 0 sized components) could not be measured since measurement is inherently a means of comparing two finite values.

To elaborate, imagine infinity as a hyper-dimensional realm of values that expands forever in every direction. Note that infinity must expand forever in every direction since if it stopped it would need to have borders which would mean there would need to be values “outside” of those borders which would also mean it wouldn’t be infinity. Now if infinity is imagined as a realm of values and contains the highest amount of value possible, then all finite numbers would essentially need to be subsets of this infinity. This is because they cannot be imagined outside of infinity since if they were, that infinity would not be infinity since it did not contain those numbers outside of it.

Therefore, any finite number would need to essentially be a “division” of infinity within the infinity. Now in order for such a number to be measured its “subset” within the infinity must be “separated” within the infinity and then contextualized by an observer. This is because only

when a value is “separated” within the infinity can it be finitely analyzed. However, if such a number was never “finite” then it could never be separated from infinity and therefore never be measured or analyzed. For its “snapshot” could never be taken and then measured.

Infinity cannot have configurations

This is simply a means to convey that “infinity itself is objective”. This is because infinity is limitless, cannot be separated out from itself and is therefore always just one whole thing. Since measurement presupposes finiteness and contextualization, something that is infinite and non-subjective or contextual (since it cannot be separated out from infinity since it IS infinity) cannot be measured. This renders infinity as “always objective” since it can have no subjective configurations of itself and therefore must always exist as one “infinite whole”. For only finite “subsets” of infinity can have conceivable configurations since configurations themselves require the “division” of infinity into its components. Obviously, infinity itself can never be totally split up into its components since it is limitless in its expansion so cannot have “configurations” in this way. This establishes infinity as always “objective” since there can be no 2 ways to organize it totally since as a whole it is always one thing. However, finite components of infinity can be contextualized and split up into different configurations of themselves. These “configurations” of themselves essentially give them subjective existences and therefore allow them to then be “measured” in relation to one another by means of comparing “the finite sizes of their configured components”.

Comparing Cardinalities of Infinite Sets Objectively

From here it can be seen how infinite sets cannot be “compared” to one another since they each are objective in that they expand forever, are not finite and therefore cannot be subjectively contextualized or measured. That being said, in the case of comparing the cardinality of numbers between 1 and 2 and those between 1 and 3 - both such sets are in fact finite (since one’s value is 1 and another’s value is 2). Therefore both of these sets must already be separated out from infinity and then already be contextualized since they are both finitely valued. Therefore splitting them into their most indivisible components should be possible since they are already isolated from infinity!

Now on the surface this seems true - after all if an “infinite amount of value” can be likened to an ever expanding clay, then surely if finite “pieces” of said clay are cut out from the total block of clay then the two pieces of clay can be “subdivided” amongst themselves and then compared. However what is being neglected here, is the gap between the subjective nature of things and the objective nature things. Therefore if one piece of clay of size 1 is used to represent the “cardinality of numbers between 1 and 2” and another piece of clay of size 2 is used to represent the “cardinality of numbers between 1 and 3”, then the two both have a “subjective” existence and also an “objective” existence. For when they are separated out of the infinite whole of clay they are finite. However, when divided infinitely amongst themselves the two pieces of clay become nothing “finite” since they “appear” as nothing. This is because of course since 0 is the only indivisible number, when they are infinitely subdivided they must consist of an infinite amount of pieces of clay each without any size.

However these “pieces” of clay each of 0 size are however not nothing but rather just “objective”. They “appear” to be nothing because they lack size but in reality are just the actual “objective” amalgamations of themselves. For anything objectively is essentially defined by its most infinitesimal components. It are these “components” that make up the individual true nature of a value. This is because the division of “anything” into its 0 sized components essentially exhibits the true foundations of said “anything”. The “anything” then that is contextualized by observers and “measured” is simply just a subjective amalgamation of those “true foundations”. In reality however such “true foundations” make up every single subjective amalgamation of themselves. In this way they are “objective”.

This can be seen by the example of “clay” sculptures. Suppose that a class of children are each provided a tub of clay. When they first receive these “tubs” of clay, each tub of clay is objectively the same - each only a tub of clay. However, each child can mold said tub of clay into different things. One forms a clay lion while another fashions a clay castle. The subjective amalgamations of the clay all take on different “forms” within the classroom though objectively they are still all just “clay”.

The values of 1 and 2 are similar in this sense as they are both just subjective manifestations of the clay of “0s” (or what Massimo Melli calls physical zeroes). Both are simply made of an infinite amount of “0s” yet essentially are subjectively manifested as 2 different things.

Now finally, one more question could be asked - well if one’s manifestation is of size 2 while another’s is of size 1 then shouldn’t the one of size 2 always be bigger? After all if one child starts with double the amount of clay as another then shouldn’t that child also be able to build a statue twice as large?

Well classically, this would be true. However, if each child was to take every iota of clay and divide it down into small enough components eventually the iotas of clay that would result would be invisible to them. This is because these pieces of clay would now just be molecules that are too “small” to notice by the human eye. However, if such a piece of clay was divided infinitely eventually it would consist of “nothing”. This is because such molecules of clay would need to be able to be divided until they are indivisible. However, when each component of clay is of “size 0” it can be said that was once a finite block of clay is now an “amalgamation of infinite 0s” or infinite components of nothingness. Classically, division of this sort would be impossible, though theoretically these “infinite zeroes” represent the true nature of any finite amount of clay. Furthermore, theoretically with “infinite zeroes”, one can rebuild a clay state of any size.

This is because what the infinite zeroes actually are $0/0$ s because infinity $(X/0) * 0 = 0/0$. This $0/0$ can be set to any possible number. For example if $2*0 = 0$ then $0/0$ could equal 2, furthermore if $3*0 = 0$ then $0/0$ could equal 3. This shows how an infinite amount of zeroes can be reconstructed into a value of any size cause an infinite amount of zeroes is essentially a “superposition” of all possible values (in the words of Walter Gomide).

Back to Comparing Cardinalities

Therefore, an infinite amount of zeroes can be constructed into either of the values 1 or 2. Since the distance between 1 and 2 is of value 1 and the distance between 1 and 3 is of value 2, this explains how all such numbers actually “contain” the same amount of components. After all, objectively both 1 and 2 can be subdivided into an infinite amount of 0's. At this point they are described by a superposition of all values or 0/0. This is because 0/0 is no longer 1 or 2, but rather their objective amalgamations - just an infinite number of 0's. Therefore, if a value of 1 was broken down into an infinite amount of zeroes it could then be reconstructed into a value of 2 from those infinite amount of 0's. In this way objectively 1 has the same number of “infinitesimal” components as 2 and no paradoxes are present. Therefore, both the cardinalities of values in the sets of numbers between 1 and 2 and 1 and 3 are the same and both infinities can be said to be of the same “objective size”.